

USING SITUATIONAL TASKS IN FORMING STUDENTS THINKING

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Abstract: This article reveals the meaning, forms and content of situational tasks, role-playing and business games that allow students to form clinical thinking in medical higher educational institutions in the process of mastering the subject of obstetrics and gynecology.

Key words: medicine, thinking, clinical thinking, activity, process, modeling, imitation, problem situation, situational task, game, result.

Enter. Currently, in the system of higher medical education, great attention is paid to the development and implementation of optimal teaching methods (diagnostics, treatment-prophylaxis and other problems) that will allow students not only to form deep theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications, but also to use them in practice in the future.

Therefore, the main characteristic of a graduate of a medical university is the combination of professional competence and clinical thinking skills.

The formation of clinical thinking is considered a long-term process, and it is gradually developed during the study of obstetrics and gynecology by students.

The purpose of mastering this subject is to prepare physiological and complicated pregnant women for independent care, treatment, diagnosis, and prevention of postpartum complications; important gynecological diseases, emergency care at the pre-hospital stage, rehabilitation after pathological childbirth and gynecological diseases, and family planning and reproductive health protection measures.

At the same time, we help students understand the identified signs of pathology, put forward hypotheses about possible diseases; thinking in terms of forming a differential diagnosis and clinical diagnosis; determine the possible sequence of factors and situations that make up the etiology and pathogenesis of the disease; forecasting, making a treatment plan and evaluating its results; we should also include the skills of planning preventive and rehabilitation measures. Because the success of professional activities depends to a large extent on the manifestation of operational thinking based on clinical thinking.

Russian scientists N.A. Ardamatsky, V.L. Bogdanovich, V.G. Vogralik, P.V. Kopnin, B.K. Lozovsky, I.E. Farber, S.P. Fedorov's studies have studied the conceptual basis of the content and manifestation of clinical thinking.

Uzbek scientists M.T.Khamdamova, G.N.Kurbanova, M.N.Batriddinova, K.I.Zhoraeva, Z.N. Boboeva and others in the direction of the formation, specific aspects, characteristics, and manifestations of professional, operative and clinical thinking conducted scientific research.

Foreign scientists R. Paul, N. N. Nepeivoda, D. Cluster, D. Halpern's work combines critical, operational and clinical thinking the possibilities of manifestation in the process of human activity are indicated.

The main part. In the educational process, it is appropriate to use educational and control situational tasks in order to choose research methods for forming the clinical thinking of students, differential diagnosis of diseases, and the use of adequate medical tactics.

During our pedagogical work at the Bukhara State Medical Institute, including the teaching of obstetrics and gynecology, we use several types of situational tasks.

First of all, these are tasks aimed at solving typical specific situations that require a short and clear answer, aimed at developing and strengthening obstetric knowledge among students.

The second type of tasks are more complex clinical tasks that require sufficient theoretical knowledge and contain a lot of information, which can be solved by different approaches.

These types of clinical tasks allow to develop the student's clinical thinking, his ability to make quick decisions in clinical situations and choose the right medical tactics.

The third type of situations has an extended logical structure and includes tasks consisting of programmed learning and control elements.

These situational assignments provide an opportunity for students to develop clinical and logical thinking in the diagnosis process and require fundamental knowledge of Obstetrics and Gynecology.

Organizational-active games ensure the organization of collective mental activity of students based on the interaction of all students in the group in the process of developing a problem situation and analyzing it while maintaining the personal position of each.

Role-playing games are characterized by the fact that students are given a specific task or problem and the roles in solving it are distributed among the participants.

Business and business games are organized according to the nature of decisions and actions taken in strict accordance with the next events with the dynamic development of the situation, task or problem as a method of teaching professional activity by modeling close to real conditions. Business games are a form of re-creating the subject or social content of professional activity, modeling the system of relationships specific to this type of practice. The purpose of the game is to develop the activity of its participants in a special (game-like) simulation model.

These games use actual, realistic, typical, complete, uplifting and developmental situations.

During the educational process, we offered several variants of clinical games depending on the level of difficulty.

The first option is "doctor-patient". In this, the conditions of the doctor's intellectual professional activity aimed at identifying diseases and treating the patient are modeled. This form of the game is organized in the range of game activity of one student and a whole group of students together with the teacher.

The second option is "Consilium", in addition to the treating doctor, consultants are involved in the game, and therefore different players play the role of doctors of different specialties and levels of training.

The third variant of the clinical game is called Ward Doctor, as the ward doctor examines and supervises several patients on a daily basis, in order to model a real situation, students play the role of patients at different stages of examination, disease and treatment.

One of the most difficult and complex business games is "Women's advice" - "Perinital hospital". because the organization of these games includes not only a clinical but also an organizational aspect.

Summary. In our country, great attention is paid to the rapid development of the social sphere, strengthening the health of the population, and developing effective mechanisms for the training of future medical workers. Development of professional knowledge, skills and thinking of future specialists on the basis of modern technologies, formation of innovative thinking and potential in them is gaining importance in teaching the science of gynecology..

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